

A Cross-Sectional Analysis of Climate Change Anxiety and Depression Among Female Smallholder Farmers in Ghana: The Moderating Role of Social Capital

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ABSTRACT

Climate change poses a significant threat to agricultural communities globally, with female farmers in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) disproportionately affected. As climate-related stressors intensify, there is growing concern about the mental health consequences for these vulnerable populations. However, limited research has explored the specific association between climate change anxiety (CCA) and depression among female smallholder farmers. This study aimed to examine the association between climate change anxiety and depression among female smallholder farmers in Ghana and to assess whether social capital modifies this relationship. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 828 female smallholder farmers in Ghana. CCA was assessed using the 13-item scale developed by Clayton and Karazsia, while depression was measured using a 7-item abridged version of the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21-D). Multiple linear regression models were employed to analyze both direct associations and interaction effects, controlling for potential confounders. Climate change anxiety was significantly associated with higher depression scores ($\beta = 0.14$, 95%CI=.196, .342, $p < 0.001$). This relationship remained significant across age groups: 18–64 years ($\beta = 0.29$, 95%CI=.145, $p < 0.001$) and 65+ years ($\beta = 0.12$, 95%CI=.185, .342, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, social capital significantly moderated the relationship between CCA and depression, serving a protective role ($\beta = -0.10$, 95%CI%= -1.14, -.171, $p < 0.001$). The findings suggest that strengthening social capital may serve as an effective buffer against the mental health impacts of climate change.

Keywords: *Climate change anxiety; mental health; female smallholder farmers; social capital; Ghana*

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INTRODUCTION

Global climate change remains the most pressing challenge of the 21st century, heavily impacting ecosystems and human well-being, including health, infrastructure, and livelihoods (Riden et al., 2021). Female smallholder farmers, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) where they operate family-run farms on a limited scale (typically less than 10 hectares or 24 acres) and rely heavily on family labor in rural settings (Fanzo, 2017), are among the most vulnerable populations facing the impacts of climate change. Their dependence on the environment for survival coupled with limited access to resources and support systems, creates unique challenges in the face of a changing climate. In recent years, growing attention has been given to the role of social capital, (SC) defined broadly as the networks, norms, and trust that facilitate cooperation and mutual support, as a critical social determinant of health and a strategy for building resilience among rural farmers (Haines et al., 2011; McKenzie & Harpham, 2006). For female smallholder farmers in SSA, SC often serves as an informal safety net, which may moderate the psychological effects of climate stressors, by enhancing resilience and buffering against emotional distress. Yet, its relevance in the climate change-mental health nexus remains poorly understood. Mounting evidence suggests that climate change will have far-reaching consequences for human health, with mental health being a critical area of concern (Reyes et al., 2023; Thoits, 2011). Climate stressors like rising temperatures, drought events, and unreliable rainfall patterns can exacerbate existing vulnerabilities and increase the risk of mental health conditions like depression (Cianconi et al., 2020; Daghigh Yazd et al., 2019).

Depression, characterized by feelings of sadness, hopelessness, and loss of interest, is a leading cause of disability, premature death, and increased risk of suicide (Fiske et al., 2009; Jackson et al., 2014; Sivertsen et al., 2015) and disability adjusted life years (DALYs) (Zhang et al., 2023) worldwide. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that depression prevalence among the general population ranges from 10-20% (WHO, 2017). Crucially, individuals with depression have a 40% higher risk of premature death compared to those without (WHO, 2017). Beyond personal suffering, depression amplifies the functional disabilities caused by physical illness, interferes with treatment and rehabilitation, increases healthcare utilization and hospitalization, and ultimately contributes to a decline in a person's physical functioning (Tsutsumimoto et al., 2016; Windle & Windle, 2013; Yang et al., 2020). The burden of depression is particularly severe for female smallholder farmers in SSA, largely due to their over-dependence on the environment for livelihoods, limited access to mental healthcare and resources, and often challenging socio-cultural conditions (Gyasi & Phillips, 2020; Lagu et al., 2013). Therefore, identifying the key contributing factors to depression among female smallholder farmers is crucial to help public health tailor disease prevention strategies, and to ensure healthy well-being among female smallholder farmers and agricultural sustainability.

Climate change anxiety (CCA), defined broadly as negative cognitive, emotional, and behavioral responses associated with concerns about climate change, has been linked to several mental health problems, including depression, stress, anxiety, insomnia, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), grief, loss of identity, and suicidal ideation (Cianconi et al., 2020; Padhy et al., 2015; Polain et al., 2011). This psychological condition is closely intertwined with depression, as prolonged anxiety about climate change may lead to feelings of hopelessness, helplessness, and despair, which are key symptoms of depressive disorders (Berry et al., 2011; Schwartz et al., 2023). Conversely, individuals with pre-existing depression may be more susceptible to CCA, creating a potential cyclical relationship (Pihkala, 2022). Prior data suggest that climate anxiety tends to occur particularly among farmers, particularly among female smallholder farmers (Abunyewah et al., 2023), given that their livelihood is directly linked to the environment, coupled with their weak adaptive capacity to the impacts of climate change (Rothschild

& Haase, 2023). Some general population-based studies from Western countries and Asian societies have shown that higher climate anxiety is associated with mental and psychiatric disorders, including depression. For instance, among 130 Italian adult cohorts, Innocenti et al. (2023) found that higher climate anxiety was associated with higher generalized anxiety. In a cross-sectional study among 438 American adult's cohort aged 18-28 years, Schwartz et al. (2023) noted that higher climate anxiety levels were significantly associated with generalized anxiety symptoms and higher odds of mental health disorders. A systematic review of 18 studies by Léger-Goodes et al. (2022) confirmed that children who experience eco-anxiety are more likely to develop ill mental health outcomes, including the onset of depression, anxiety, and emotional distress like sadness, anger, and fear.

However, emerging evidence indicates that a higher degree of SC and support is associated with a lower risk of psychological distress in a dose-response manner (Gyasi, 2019). Conversely, a lack of intergenerational SC has been shown to be a major risk factor for poor mental health, including the onset of depressive symptoms (Haines et al., 2011; McKenzie & Harpham, 2006). Indeed, various levels of social relationships and support among female smallholder farmers may potentially buffer and delay or counter probable mental disorders (Nakagomi et al., 2021), including depression, helping those affected to maintain the highest degree of quality of life. Indeed, strong SC allows female smallholder farmers to stay active, productive, socially connected, and engaged in the community (Torkelsson, 2007) and consistently associated with wide-ranging psychological well-being (Gyasi, 2019). However, evidence is almost missing in the SSA context regarding studies examining the interactive impacts of SC on the CCA-depression link.

Despite the growing recognition of climate-induced mental health challenges (Innocenti et al., 2023; Schwartz et al., 2023), there are several notable gaps in the literature. First, while studies have linked CCA to adverse mental health outcomes in general populations across Europe, North America, and Asia (Berry et al., 2011; Cianconi et al., 2020; Schwartz et al., 2023), their generalizability to the SSA context may be limited due to significant cultural, environmental, and structural differences, and thus require further investigation. Consequently, there is a critical need for context-specific research, particularly among female smallholder farmers in Ghana who face heightened exposure and unique vulnerabilities. Second, although SC is acknowledged as a protective factor in mental health, its potential moderating role in the specific relationship between CCA and depression remains poorly understood, especially in agrarian, low-resource contexts. This study therefore employed a cross-sectional, community-based approach to examine the association between climate change anxiety and depression among female smallholder farmers in Ghana, while also assessing the moderating effect of social capital. In doing so, it directly addresses the existing geographic and demographic gaps in the literature by generating context-specific empirical evidence from SSA. Moreover, by statistically testing the interaction between SC and CCA in predicting depression, the study advances current knowledge on the mechanisms through which informal support systems can mitigate climate-related psychological stress. This evidence is of great importance for public health professionals, clinicians, and policymakers. Crucially, it will help provide critical insights for policymakers and public health professionals in SSA, guiding the development of targeted interventions such as community-based support systems, capacity-building programs, and the integration of mental health services into agricultural extension services. These knowledge bases will help design effective strategies to address mental health challenges, promote resilience, and ensure sustainable agricultural productivity in SSA.

METHODS

Study setting

This study was conducted in the Bosomtwe District, Ashanti Region, Ghana (Figure 1). Encompassing approximately 422.5 square kilometers, the district lies between longitudes 1° 15' East and 1° 46' West and latitudes 6° 24' South and 6° 43' North. It borders Asokwa Municipal, Ejisu Municipal, Ashanti Bekwai Municipal, Bosome-Freho District, and Atwima-Kwanwoma District. The district boasts a diverse landscape and socioeconomic context critical to understanding the mental health of female smallholder farmers in the face of climate change. The district has a projected population of 119,730 with a slight female majority (52.3%). The climate is wet sub-equatorial, with average temperatures ranging from 24°C to 27.8°C. High relative humidity prevails year-round, peaking in the morning and dropping in the afternoon. The rainy season spans June and October, contributing to an annual average rainfall of 1650 mm. Marked by a sloping topography, the district features water bodies like Lake Bosomtwe and rivers including Oda, Butu, Siso, Supan, and Adanbanwe.

Figure 1. Location map of the study communities

The underlying geology is dominated by middle Precambrian rocks forming a plateau. Falling within the South-East Ecological Zone, the area boasts a wet semi-deciduous environment with nutrient-rich forest ochrosols supporting agriculture in remote communities. Agriculture is a vital livelihood for over 62.9% of the population. Major crops include cocoa, plantain, cassava, maize, vegetables, and rice. Livestock rearing (goats, chicken, pigs, cattle) and small-scale fish farming (particularly around Lake Bosomtwe) supplement agricultural activities. Female smallholder in the district plays a significant role, contributing through beekeeping, vegetable farming, and off-farm activities. The district boasts 23 health facilities offering various healthcare services, including mental health care, to residents and

those from neighboring areas. The district provides unique grounds for this study due to its higher proportion of female smallholder farmers, who are heavily involved in agriculture and off-farm activities despite limited healthcare access. While the district has 23 health facilities, access to healthcare, especially for mental health services, remains challenging in remote areas. Climate variability, including unreliable rainfall, extreme temperatures and strong winds, further exacerbates the vulnerability of subsistence farming in Ghana, including the Bosomtwe district. The findings from this study would therefore be comparable and generalizable to other rural areas in Ghana and SSA, where similar socio-economic and environmental conditions exist. Data collection was carried out over 7 weeks (from 15th February 2025 to 5th April 2025).

Study design sampling and data collection process

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to assess CCA, depression, SC, and health experiences among female smallholder farmers in Bosomtwe. Given the decentralized nature of smallholder farming in Bosomtwe, a simple random sampling technique was employed to select female farmers at the household level. To ensure representativeness and minimize bias, a multi-stage sampling technique was employed. First, the district was divided into three zones; high, medium, and low agricultural activity, based on how active farming was in each area and the presence of female smallholder farmers. This was done through field observations and discussions with district officials and agricultural extension officers. In the second stage, four communities were randomly selected from each zone, yielding a total of 12 communities. This zoning ensured diversity in agricultural intensity and the presence of female smallholder farmers across the district. In the third stage, houses within each selected community were sampled using systematic random sampling. In smaller communities (fewer than 250 houses), every third house was selected; in larger communities (250+ houses), every fifth house was chosen. The starting house in each community was determined using a lottery method, where research assistants drew a numbered slip from a container to identify the initial house. Subsequent houses were selected using the fixed interval rule. In houses with multiple eligible participants, the eldest woman farmer was selected. Inclusion criteria required participants to be female smallholder farmers aged 18 or older, actively engaged in farming, and residing in the district. The age requirement of 18 was set to ensure that all participants were legally recognized as adults, capable of providing informed consent, and are more likely to make independent farming decisions. Participants who did not meet these criteria or declined consent were excluded. The target population of female subsistence farmers in Bosomtwe was estimated at 5,336, based on data from the 2010 Population and Housing Census.

To determine the minimum required sample size, Cochran's formula for sample size estimation was used, considering a 95% confidence interval (CI), a 5% margin of error, and an assumed default prevalence of 0.5. The calculation yielded a minimum sample size of 384 participants. To account for potential nonresponse and missing data, an oversampling rate of 38% was applied, leading to an estimated required sample size of approximately 576 participants. However, to maximize statistical power, support moderation, ensure stable estimates in models with multiple covariates, and ensure robust analysis (Cohen, 1992; Green, 1991), a total of 842 responses were collected. This aligns with best practices in psychological and health research, where larger samples improve the detection of small-to-moderate effect sizes and subgroup generalizability (Tartour et al., 2024). Following data cleaning, 11 responses were removed due to incompleteness, and 3 responses were excluded as extreme outliers. After these exclusions, the final analytic sample comprised 828 participants. This

response rate was considered sufficient to ensure statistical power (85%) and representativeness while balancing resource constraints and feasibility (Cochran, 1977).

To enhance efficiency and ensure wider geographical coverage, the Rapid Rural Appraisal technique, which refers to a set of participatory, qualitative methods used to quickly and systematically collect information from rural communities (Chambers, 1994) were employed. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire, supplemented by face-to-face interviews lasting approximately 30–45 minutes to enhance accuracy and depth. To ensure cultural appropriateness, the questionnaire was initially developed in English and later translated into Twi, the predominant local dialect, following WHO translation protocols (Peters et al., 2007).

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Committee on Human Research, Publications and Ethics (CHRPE) at the School of Medical Sciences, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana (Ref: CHRPE/AP/0103/25) (approved on February 2025). Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. To ensure confidentiality, all identifying information was anonymized, and strict ethical protocols were followed to protect participants' rights. The research team also adhered to cultural norms and values to ensure respectful engagement with the local farming communities. To mitigate self-report biases, trained local research assistants (6 research assistants, trained over a period of three weeks prior to data collection phase) conducted the interviews in participants' preferred language. In addition, to reduce recall bias, respondents were asked to report on their recent experiences, particularly in relation to CCA and depression, over the seven days. This approach minimized inaccuracies due to long-term recall. Furthermore, to address social desirability bias, respondents were reassured that their answers would remain confidential and used solely for research purposes. This, coupled with face-to-face interviews, helped ensure that participants could respond freely and truthfully without fear of judgment.

Measures

Quantitative measures used in this study included the following:

Depression (Outcome variable). Depression was our dependent variable and was assessed with seven-item questions abridged from the DASS-21 scale by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) (Beck, 1996). The DASS-21 version was used as it has a 97% concurrence with the 42-item version. This scale consists of three self-report sub-constructs measuring depression (DASS-D), anxiety (DASS-A), and stress (DASS-S). The scale has been validated in various cultural contexts, including African populations, where it has demonstrated strong reliability and validity in measuring mental health symptoms (Coker et al., 2018; Dreyer et al., 2019). The use of this scale is appropriate for the Ghanaian rural farming context, as it is simple and adaptable to rural settings with limited literacy levels and time constraints, ensuring a practical and culturally relevant tool for assessing depressive symptoms in this population. The depression scale assesses dysphoria, hopelessness, devaluation of life, self-deprecation, lack of interest/involvement, anhedonia, and inertia. Participants rated their experiences over the past seven days on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). Items included statements such as "I do not seem to experience any positive feelings at all." The total score ranged from 7 to 35, with higher scores reflecting greater depressive symptoms. The scale demonstrated acceptable internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.76$) in this study. We conducted cognitive pretesting with a small group of Ghanaian female farmers to ensure clarity and contextual relevance. For analysis, the total

depression score was treated as a continuous variable, with no transformations or categorization applied.

Climate change anxiety (Exposure). Climate change anxiety was assessed with Clayton and Karazsia's 13-item scale. This scale showed good reliability and validity in a U.S. adult sample and a Filipino emerging adult sample (Clayton, 2020; Reyes et al., 2023). The questions assess cognitive (e.g., "Thinking about climate change makes it difficult for me to sleep") and functional (e.g., "My concerns about climate change interfere with my ability to get work or school assignments done") impairments in response to climate change. Participants were asked to rate these items on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (almost always). The overall score of CCA ranged from 13 to 65, with higher scores indicating greater levels of CCA. Reliability in the current sample was acceptable (Cronbach alpha (α)=0.85). The total score for CCA was used as a continuous variable. While this scale was originally validated in non-African populations, it demonstrated strong internal consistency in our Ghanaian rural sample and was cognitively pretested to ensure comprehension and cultural relevance.

Social Capital (Moderator). Social capital was our moderator variable. We adapted the 16-item Personal Social Capital Scale (PSCS) (Wang et al., 2014). Thus, we made minor language adjustments to suit the local dialect and cultural expressions, and we also conducted cognitive pretesting with a small group of Ghanaian female farmers to ensure clarity and contextual relevance. The PSCS measures bonding and bridging SC, capturing both individual-level social relationships (e.g., friendships, trust) and broader perceptions of community-level structures and resources (e.g., availability of local organizations). Each item was measured on a 5-point Likert scale, where 1 implies strongly disagree and 5 indicates strong agreement. The PSCS-16 scale has been used in numerous studies and is valid and reliable ($\alpha = 0.9$). Among the items measuring personal social capital are "I have many friends," "I trust many of my fellows/co-workers," and "There are many governmental, political, economic, and social organizations that exist in this community." The overall score of SC ranged from 16 to 80, with higher scores indicating greater SC (Cronbach alpha=0.78). The total score for SC was used as a continuous variable in this study.

Covariates. Socio-demographic attributes, mental health conditions, and climate change-related variables that have been reported in previous studies to be associated with mental health, specifically depression (see, e.g., Back & Lee, 2011; Zivin et al., 2010), were included as controls in the current analysis. Age (categorical) (18-64 = 1; 65+ = 2), marital status (single/never married/divorced/widowed = 1; married or partnered = 2), ethnic differences (Akan=1; others/Ewe/Mole-Dagbani/Ga = 2), crop type (food crop=1; cash crop=2), landownership (own outright = 1; others/leased/tenant = 2) were dichotomous variables. Education was classified into three levels, using the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED-1997; Schneider, 2013), including primary education or none = 1; high/secondary school education = 2; tertiary/post-secondary education = 3. Climate-related variables, including climate change experience, was self-assessed. The participants were asked three questions about how often they, others around them, and places important to them, had already been affected by climate change (e.g., "I have been directly affected by climate change" on a scale of 1 = "never" to 5 = "almost always," adapted from (Clayton, 2020). The total score ranged 3–15 with a higher score indicating higher level of climate change experience. Reliability for this variable was acceptable (Cronbach alpha = 0.90). Climate change knowledge was assessed with 11 questions in four subscales (adapted from Tobler et al., 2012). Responses were recorded on a 3-point scale: correct = 1; incorrect = 2, not certain = 3. The total score ranged 11–33 with a lower score indicating higher knowledge (Cronbach's alpha = 0.74). The questions were about the physical effects of CO₂ and greenhouse gases, the causes and consequences of climate change, and action-related knowledge.

Examples include “At the same quantity, CO₂ is more harmful to the climate than methane” and “climate change is mainly caused by human activities.” Generalized anxiety symptoms were assessed using the 7-item Generalized Anxiety Disorder scale (GAD-7; Spitzer et al., 2006), which measures symptom frequency over the past two weeks using a 4-point scale (0 = not at all to 3 = nearly every day). Total scores ranged from 0 to 21, with higher scores indicating greater anxiety severity. Internal consistency in the current study was acceptable (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.78$). The instruments were cognitively pretested among Ghanaian rural participants to ensure clarity, comprehension, and contextual relevance.

Data analysis

Frequency and descriptive statistics were calculated to describe our data. The normality of continuous data was determined using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, and the assumptions were confirmed before substantive analysis. Given the sensitivity of this test in large samples we also inspected skewness, kurtosis values, and Q–Q plots to evaluate normality. To ensure the regression assumptions were met, we also checked for linearity, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity. Linearity was assessed by inspecting scatter plots of the outcome variable (depression) against the predictor variables (CCA and SC), showing a linear relationship. Homoscedasticity was confirmed by examining residuals versus fitted values, which displayed no discernible pattern, indicating constant variance. Multicollinearity was tested using variance inflation factors (VIFs), and all VIFs were below 5, suggesting no significant multicollinearity. We performed Pearson’s zero-order correlations in the bivariate analysis to evaluate the interrelationships among the core continuous study variables. Finally, multiple linear regression models (ordinary least squares [OLS]) were used in which depression (outcome) was regressed on the major independent variable, CCA while controlling for potential confounding variables. Model 1 regressed depression outcome on CCA only. Model 2 added the moderator (SC) variable, climate-related predictors, and socio-demographic and health-related factors as control variables. Finally, the full model (Model 3) included respondents’ interaction term (CCA \times SC) (moderation). For the regression analyses, the enter method was used to include all relevant covariates simultaneously based on theoretical and empirical justifications, rather than stepwise selection methods such as forward or backward selection. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant, and all analyses were performed using SPSS v.25.0 (IBM, Armonk, NY). All analyses were conducted using complete case analysis (listwise deletion), as missing data were minimal (<5%) and determined to be missing completely at random (MCAR) based on Little’s MCAR test.

RESULTS

Sample characteristics

The final analytic sample included 828 adult female smallholder farmers aged ≥ 18 years in Bosomtwe, Ghana. The sample characteristics are presented in **Table 1**. Generally, the majority of the respondents were aged 18-64 (81.2%), single (59.4%), and having primary or no formal education (72.5%). The relatively high proportion of single women in the sample may reflect local demographic and socio-economic dynamics, including delayed or non-marriage due to economic precarity, widowhood, or migration of spouses for work, which is common patterns in many rural Ghanaian contexts. This trend may influence coping capacities and access to support networks, which are critical in shaping both mental health outcomes and adaptive responses to climate stressors. Participants are largely Akan (84.1%), with household sizes typically ranging from 4-6 members (41.3%). Most respondents operate small farms of 1-5 acres (75.4%), focus on food crops (79.0%), and own their land outright (65.9%).

Furthermore, on average, climate change anxiety level was 57.48 (SD=9.64), depression was 30.73 (SD=3.01), climate change experience 10.27(SD=1.72), climate change knowledge 12.04 (SD = 2.57), and personal social capital 65.09 (SD = 6.07).

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variables	Frequency (N=828)	Percent (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (years)				
18-64	672	81.2		
65+	156	18.8		
Marital status				
Married	336	40.6		
Singled	492	59.4		
Education				
Primary/none	600	72.5		
Secondary	210	25.4		
Tertiary	18	2.2		
Ethnic group				
Akan	696	84.1		
Others	132	15.9		
Household size				
1-3	204	24.6		
4-6	342	41.3		
7-10	228	27.5		
11 and above	54	6.5		
Farm size				
1 -5 Acres	624	75.4		
6-10 Acres	138	16.7		
11-15 Acres	60	7.2		
16+ Acres	6	.7		
Crop type				
Food crop	654	79.0		
Cash crop	174	21.0		
Landownership				
Own outright	546	65.9		
Others (leased, tenant)	282	34.1		
CCA			57.48	9.64
GAS			27.20	2.8
Depression			30.73	3.01
CCE			10.27	1.72
CLK			12.04	2.57
PSC			65.09	6.07

Note: CCA—climat change anxiety; PSC—personal social capital; CCK—Climate change knowledge; GAS—generalized anxiety symptoms

Correlations

Table 2 presents the zero-order Pearson's correlations matrix for the core and continuous study variables. The results show a significant positive correlation between depression and CCA ($r = 0.14, p < 0.05$), indicating that higher levels of CCA are associated with increased depression. Climate change experience also demonstrated a significant positive correlation with CCA ($r = 0.11, p < 0.05$), suggesting that individuals with more climate change experiences tend to have higher levels of CCA. Interestingly, the correlation between climate change experience and depression was non-significant. While this may appear, counterintuitive given prior literature linking cumulative climate stressors to adverse mental

health, it is possible that farmers in this setting have developed coping mechanisms or have normalized environmental shocks as part of their lived realities, thereby buffering the direct emotional impact of these experiences on depression symptoms. No other significant correlations were observed.

Table 2. Zero-order Pearson's correlations matrix for the core and continuous study variables

		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Depression	1				
2.	CCA	0.14**	1			
3.	SC	-0.05	0.01	1		
4.	CCE	-0.02	0.11**	-0.01	1	
5.	CCK	0.05	0.02	0.02	-0.01	1

CCA—climate change anxiety; SC—social capital; CCE—Climate change experience; CCK—Climate change knowledge

*** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.005$; * $p < 0.05$

Main regression models

In **Table 3**, our regression estimates in model 1 showed that CCA was significantly and positively associated with higher odds of depression ($\beta = 0.14$, 95%CI=.196, .342, $p < 0.001$). In model 2, CCA remains a significant predictor of depression ($\beta = 0.17$, 95%CI=.193, .337, $p < 0.001$), consistent with the previous model. Stress ($\beta = 0.30$, 95%CI=.148, .622, $p < 0.001$) and PTSD ($\beta = 0.39$, 95%CI=.017, .176, $p < 0.001$) also emerged as strong positive predictors of depression. SC showed a small but significant negative association with depression ($\beta = -0.06$, 95%CI=-.168, -.030, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that higher SC may slightly reduce depressive symptoms. While the effect sizes for CCA and SC are relatively small (β values in the 0.1–0.2 range), they are statistically significant and substantively meaningful within the context of population-level mental health research. These findings suggest that even modest increases in CCA may contribute to higher depressive symptoms, and slight improvements in SC could offer protective benefits. Education level had a mixed effect, with secondary education showing a significant positive association with depression compared to primary or no education ($\beta = 0.33$, 95%CI=.007, .176, $p < 0.001$). This unexpected pattern may reflect increased awareness of climate-related stressors, unmet aspirations, or greater psychosocial pressure among more educated women, particularly those with secondary education who may still face significant barriers to economic mobility in rural contexts. In contrast, tertiary education showed no significant effect. Age was a significant factor, with those aged 18–64 showing higher levels of depression compared to those 65 and older ($\beta = 0.17$, 95%CI=.170, .633, $p < 0.001$). Food crop farmers reported significantly higher levels of depression than cash crop farmers ($\beta = 0.10$, 95%CI = .128, .592, $p < 0.01$). Climate change knowledge, climate change experience, marital status, and land ownership did not show significant associations with depression in this model.

Additionally, we analyzed the moderation effect of the relationship between exposure (CCA) and depression by SC (model 3). The interaction showed that SC significantly moderated the association between climate change anxiety and depression ($\beta = -0.10$, 95%CI% = -1.14, -.171, $p < 0.001$). The decision to test for moderation was informed by the theoretical premise that SC may function as a protective factor, potentially mitigating the psychological effects of CCA and thereby reducing the risk or severity of depression. **Figures 2** present details of the results of the hypothesized model for the study. Furthermore, we performed an age-stratification analysis on the association between CCA and depression. The age-based analysis revealed that the CCA-depression link shows significance in both the 18–64 ($\beta = 0.29$, 95%CI = .145, .480, $p < 0.000$) and the 65+ ($\beta = 0.12$, 95%CI = .185, .342, $p < 0.000$) aged groups (**Table 4**).

Table 3. Multivariable analyses of the association of climate change anxiety and covariates with depression among female smallholder farmers: Linear Regressions

	MODEL 1				MODEL 2				MODEL 3			
	β	SE	t	95%CI	β	SE	t	95%CI	β	SE	t	95%CI
CCA	0.14***	0.01	4.15	.196, .342	0.17***	0.01	5.24	.193, .337	0.17***	0.01	5.66	.200, .343
Climate change knowledge					0.03	0.02	1.01	-.083, .088	-0.02	0.03	-0.48	-.107, .066
Climate change experience					-0.01	0.02	-0.25	-1.076, .332	0.04	0.02	1.24	-.058, .306
Stress					0.30***	0.04	10.08	.148, .622	0.27***	0.04	9.25	.125, .593
PTSD					0.39***	0.03	12.83	.017, .176	0.41***	0.03	14.25	.002, .171
SC					-0.06*	0.04	-2.06	-.168, -.030	-0.06*	0.04	-2.21	-.177, -.039
Education (primary or none) ref.					-	-	-		-	-	-	
Secondary					0.33***	0.13	7.44	.007, .176	0.33***	0.13	7.43	
Tertiary					0.04	0.28	1.26	-.214, .288	0.04	0.28	1.19	-.791, .273
Marital status (married) ref.					-	-	-		-	-	-	
Single (divorced, widowed, never married)					-0.05	0.05	-1.28	-.898, .153	0.04	0.04	1.30	-.058, .306
Age (65+ years) ref.					-	-	-		-	-	-	
18-64					0.17***	0.10	5.57	.170, .633	0.15***	0.11	4.61	.130, .970
Crop farm type (cash crop) ref.												
Food crop					0.10**	0.10	3.27	.128, .592	0.10**	0.10	3.23	.151, .968
Land ownership (Others; leased, tenant) ref.					-	-	-		-	-	-	
Own outright					0.05	0.50	1.71	-.061, .456	0.06	0.50	1.90	-.265, .172
Interaction term					-	-	-		-0.10**	0.01	-3.39	-1.14, -.171
Model fitting information												
Constant	2.139	0.273	7.85	24.85, 28.83	-3.02	0.51	-5.95	20.44, 29.42	-2.45	0.44	-5.63	21.54, 30.09
R Square	0.143				0.33				0.35			
F-Statistic	17.19***				40.74***				49.16***			

Abbreviations: B – Unstandardized Coefficients; β —Standardized Coefficients; SE —standard errors; CCA– climate change anxiety; PTSD – post-traumatic stress disorder; SC – social capital; CI – confidence interval; ***p < 0.001; **p < 0.005; *p < 0.05.

Figure 2. Hypothesized model

Table 4. Age-wise analysis of the CCA-depression

Variables	Age group			
	18-64		65+	
	β	95%CI	β	95%CI
CCA	0.29***	.145, .480	0.12***	.185, .342
Climate change knowledge	0.11**	.174, 1.023	-0.12	-.090, .308
Climate change experience	0.02	-.918, .419	-0.01	-.913, .177
Stress	0.38***	.211, .790	0.27***	.030, .560
PTSD	0.41***	.022, .903	0.43***	.082, .552
SC	-0.06	-.230, .173	-0.05	-.143, .054
Education (primary or none) ref.	-		-	
Secondary	0.33***	.002, .838	0.29***	.021, .242
Tertiary	0.06	.091, .274	0.15	-.464, .130
Marital status (married) ref.	-		-	
Single (divorced, widowed, never married)	0.04	-.694, .149	0.18***	.009, .117
Crop farm type (cash crop) ref.	-		-	
Food crop	0.017	-.309, .021	0.27***	.001, .168
Land ownership (Others (leased, tenant) ref.				
Own outright	0.035	-.260, .312	0.05	-.307, .171
Model fitness				
Constant	-5.343***	3.14, 34.04	-2.22***	19.545, 29.924
R Square	0.360		0.32	
F-Statistic	13.943***	0.000	44.05***	0.000

β—Standardized Coefficients; CCA—climate change anxiety; PTSD – post-traumatic stress disorder; SC – social capital; CI – confidence interval; *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.005$; * $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

Principal findings

The primary objective of this representative study among female smallholder farmers in Bosomtwe district, Ghana was to examine whether CCA is independently related to mental disorders (depression) and, most importantly, to investigate the specific effect of SC in this relationship. Linear regressions revealed that greater levels of CCA were significantly and positively associated with higher levels of depression episodes in our sample. Similar results were observed among the two age groups in the age-wise estimations. Thus, greater CCA levels were highly associated with depression for both those in the 18-64 age group and those in the 65+ aged group. Moreover, the positive relationship between CCA and depression was significantly moderated by an increase in SC. These findings underscore the instrumental roles of stronger capital, particularly among vulnerable populations like female smallholder farmers, countering mental health disorders as a result of climate change stressors. These findings suggest the need to focus policy interventions around addressing female smallholder farmers' climate-induced mental health through increasing and enhancing social capital, particularly in the SSA context.

Our findings complement the growing literature that CCA is a psychological solid determinant of health (Hajek & König, 2023) and is associated with increased odds of depressive symptoms (Domènech-Abella et al., 2017). For example, a cross-sectional study by Schwaab et al. (2022) found among 203 German medical students that increased levels of perceived climate anxiety are associated with greater risk of stress levels. Using data from the general German adult population, among 3091 German adult cohort aged 18 to 74 years, Hajek and König (2023) noted that higher climate anxiety was associated with higher likelihood of probable depression with odds of (OR: 1.37, 95% CI: 1.25–1.50). Also, among 433 Filipinos adult cohorts aged 18-26, Reyes et al. (2023) observed that CCA was positively and significantly associated with mental disorders, with CCA predicting 13.5% of the overall mental health index variance. Our study extends the evidence and understanding regarding the association between climate anxiety and mental health (depression) to female smallholder farmers residing in the SSA context, which, to this point, has mainly been based on advanced and some Asian societies, with specific samples of either younger adults or student samples (Léger-Goodes et al., 2022; Sampaio & Sequeira, 2022). Crucially, the present study is unique and builds on the emerging literature by providing evidence of the modifying role of SC in the CCA and depressive symptoms links and provide evidence of age-wised variation of this association. Indeed, to the best of our knowledge, we are unaware of studies exploring these dynamics among female smallholder farmers' samples, particularly in Ghana.

Several plausible and non-mutually exclusive mechanistic pathways have been proposed to explain an independent link between climate change anxiety and depression, particularly among female smallholder farmers. For example, research has shown that chronic stress is a significant risk factor for depression (Conrad, 2011), particularly among vulnerable populations like female smallholder farmers who face multiple stressors (Chengane et al., 2021). CCA can lead to persistent worry and stress about unpredictable weather patterns, crop failures, and livelihood instability (Schwartz et al., 2023). This chronic stress may result in an increased allostatic load (the wear and tear on the body caused by repeated stress responses) (Juster et al., 2010). Over time, this physiological burden can dysregulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and alter neurotransmitter systems (Du & Pang, 2015), potentially leading to depressive symptoms. Second, climate anxiety is strongly associated with cognitive and psychological distress (Ojala et al., 2021; Searle & Gow, 2010). As female smallholder farmers experience repeated crop failures or economic losses due to climate change-related events,

they may develop a sense of helplessness and loss of control over their circumstances. This cognitive pattern, known as learned helplessness, is a well-established precursor to depression (Au et al., 2009). The inability to predict or control environmental factors crucial to their livelihood may erode their sense of self-efficacy and hope for the future, contributing to depressive symptoms (Jiménez-Solomon et al., 2022). Third, climate anxiety could lead to increased social isolation and community disruption. Climate change-induced environmental stressors (floods, droughts, bushfires) may potentially lead to the breakdown of social structures and support systems in rural farming communities (Chapola et al., 2024; Miller et al., 2023). Therefore, female smallholder farmers may experience increased isolation levels and may be disassociated from relevant others as community members migrate or as traditional social gatherings become less frequent due to economic pressures or environmental challenges (Abubakar et al., 2024; Yiridomoh et al., 2022). Social isolation and lack of social support are known risk factors for depression, particularly among female smallholder (Prince et al., 1997). Finally, anxiety about climate impacts on farming and livelihoods may lead to generalized anxiety disorder (GAD), characterized by excessive worry and negative emotions about various life aspects (Cianconi et al., 2020). Consequently, the persistent worry and physical symptoms of GAD can impair daily functioning, disrupt sleep patterns, cause functional impairment, and lead to avoidance behaviors, including physical inactivity and increased sedentary lifestyles (Acharibasam & Anuga, 2018; Padhy et al., 2015), all of which are crucial risk factors for the onset and progressing of depressive symptoms (Sampaio & Sequeira, 2022). It is important to note that these conjectures discussed above are based on mere speculation. Future research should consider using qualitative designs, such as in-depth interviews or focus group discussions, to explore the lived experiences and subjective interpretations of climate-related anxiety and depressive symptoms among smallholder farmers. In addition, mixed-methods longitudinal studies combining quantitative insights with biopsychosocial and physiological measurements (e.g., cortisol levels, sleep quality, HPA axis biomarkers) could help empirically test these proposed mechanisms, identify causal pathways, and inform culturally sensitive mental health interventions.

Also, our regression analysis revealed that the CCA-depression link was observed among the middle age female smallholder farmers (18-64 old years) and their older counterparts (65 above years old). Though this finding may be difficult to explain, tenable explanations have been suggested for the modification effect of age in the CCA-depression link. It is well-established fact that middle age constitutes the primary working-age population (Ahmed et al., 2016). Therefore, they may experience heightened vulnerability due to their direct engagement with and dependence on climate-sensitive livelihoods such as farming (Toader & Roman, 2015). Moreover, the middle group is more likely to bear the primary responsibility for household economic stability and future planning, making them more acutely aware of and sensitive to climate change threats than their older counterparts. Additionally, the middle age group may have a more comprehensive understanding and knowledge of long-term climate projections and their potential impacts (Lutz & Striessnig, 2015). They may, therefore, feel a greater sense of responsibility for mitigating and adapting to its effects, potentially leading to feelings of guilt or helplessness when faced with extreme climate change impacts, leading to increased depression levels (Clayton, 2020). In contrast, older female farmers may perceive climate risks through a different lens, shaped by decades of lived experiences with environmental variability and hardships (Assan et al., 2020). While they are not immune to climate-related anxiety, their emotional responses may be moderated by generational resilience, acceptance of uncertainty, or less pressure to secure long-term livelihoods (Dibakoane et al., 2022). Again, the age-specific divergence in perception and coping may also explain the relatively weaker effect size in the older group compared to the middle-aged cohort. Older individuals, while also experiencing the CCA-depression link, may encounter these challenges differently due to their life stage. Their long-standing exposure to environmental and socio-

economic changes may contribute to distinct perspectives and coping mechanisms. These findings emphasize the importance of designing interventions that consider the influence of age on mental health outcomes.

The results found significant and negative interactions of SC on the CCA and depression outcome link among female smallholder farmers. Indeed, SC may serve as a protective factor (Gyasi, 2019), potentially buffering the impact of climate change anxiety on depressive symptoms (Adam et al., 2023; Thoits, 2011), particularly among this sample. Therefore, providing social support to individuals who are climate anxious is instrumental in offsetting the onset and progression of depressive symptoms among female smallholder farmers. Crucially, strong social networks and community ties may provide emotional support, practical assistance, and shared resources that could possibly help mitigate the psychological impact of climate-related stressors (Thoits, 2011). Again, meaningful social capital can enhance individual and collective adaptive capacity, enabling farming communities to share knowledge, implement collaborative solutions, and maintain hope in the face of climate change threats, thereby counteracting negative feelings of helplessness and isolation that often contribute to depression (McKenzie & Harpham, 2006). However, it is important to recognize that SC may vary substantially across this demographic due to intersecting socio-economic and cultural conditions that shape women's access to and mobilization of support networks (Alare et al., 2022). Female smallholder farmers in rural Ghana often experience limited access to formal institutional support and instead rely heavily on informal networks such as kinship ties, communal groups, and faith-based associations (Lambrecht, 2016; Manful & Cudjoe, 2018). Moreover, disparities in literacy, land tenure, and participation in decision-making structures may create unequal levels of SC even within this group, influencing their capacity to cope with stressors like climate change (Dibakoane et al., 2022).

This study is novel and has significant merits in informing relevant public health and policy decisions to consider the role of psychological determinants of well-being like CCA in managing depression among female smallholder farmers. The results underscore the need for targeted mental health interventions specifically tailored to female smallholder farmers in the 18-64 age group, with a focus on addressing both CCA and depression. Given the protective role of SC, interventions to embed female smallholder farmers in resourceful interpersonal relationships, strengthening community cohesion and social networks may enhance their sense of belonging and potentially improve their experiences of depressive episodes. Also, improving climate change education and communication strategies, particularly for the working-age group, focusing on providing accurate information while fostering hope and empowerment, may be beneficial. Again, climate adaptation policies in the agricultural sector could explicitly incorporate mental health considerations, integrating psychological resilience into broader adaptation strategies. To effectively implement these interventions, partnerships between local non-governmental organizations (NGOs), community-based women's groups, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Food and Agriculture, and international development partners such as the WHO, FAO, and UNDP would be essential. Local NGOs and women-led community groups can facilitate outreach and peer-support structures, while the Ministry of Health could lead early screening and integration of mental health into primary care. The Ministry of Food and Agriculture could embed psychological resilience components into agricultural extension services. International donors and partners can provide funding, technical support, and monitoring frameworks to scale interventions across similar climate-vulnerable regions. We suggest public health clinicians implement early screening and intervention programs for CCA and depression, particularly in climate-vulnerable regions. Finally, policies aimed at providing economic support and promoting livelihood diversification for female smallholder farmers will be helpful in reducing financial stressors that may exacerbate mental health issues.

This current study has several strengths, including the focus on a vulnerable and often overlooked population in an innovative context, contributing to our understanding of how CCA influences the onset of depressive disorders among female smallholder farmers. Also, the application of the interactive effect analysis of SC on the CCA-depression symptoms link has helped to advance knowledge on this association, given the limited knowledge on this topic in the SSA setting. Again, our key variables, CCA, depression, and SC, were assessed on well-validated and reliable scales. However, the study has its limitations. First, given that retrospective cross-sectional data were used, causal inferences and directionality cannot be established between CCA and depression. Additionally, the potential issue of reverse causation cannot be ruled out, it's possible that individuals with depression may experience increased anxiety about climate change, rather than climate change leading to depressive symptoms. Future studies are encouraged to adopt longitudinal cohort-based tracking approaches, which would allow for temporal ordering of exposure and outcome, and more robust causal inferences. In addition, advanced analytical techniques such as structural equation modeling (SEM) or mediation analysis could further elucidate the underlying mechanisms linking CCA to depressive outcomes. Second, although our measures considered well-validated and established scales, relying solely on self-report data for our key study variables other than clinically diagnosed data may still introduce certain methodological limitations and potentially infuse social desirability bias in the results of our study. The possibility of memory bias cannot also be completely ruled out, as the nature of many social research studies. However, social research embraces this fashion of data generation. Furthermore, while we controlled for several socio-demographic, environmental, and psychosocial factors, other potential confounders such as history of mental health conditions, prior trauma, or physical health status were not accounted for. This may introduce residual confounding in the observed associations. The study's findings may not generalize beyond female smallholder farmers in rural Ghana, limiting applicability to other populations, urban settings, or regions.

CONCLUSION

This study, involving a cross-sectional representative sample of Ghanaian female smallholder farmers, explored the direct association between CCA and depression among female smallholder farmers. Our data provide empirical evidence that the significant and positive association between CCA and depression is moderated by SC, highlighting the role of SC in promoting well-being. These results have important implications for policy and public health initiatives. Strategies to manage CCA and its deconditioning depressive symptoms should consider the protective role of SC by enhancing meaningful social connectedness and cohesion, particularly among female smallholder farmers who are faced with great challenges. To enhance SC practically among female smallholder farmers, it is recommended that community-based programs focus on fostering support networks, including women's groups, cooperative farming initiatives, and local peer support systems. These programs could strengthen interpersonal relationships, increase social participation, and build collective resilience. Furthermore, creating safe spaces for knowledge exchange and emotional support, as well as promoting access to resources that facilitate social engagement, can help alleviate the mental health burden associated with climate change anxiety. While this study advances our understanding of the mental health dimensions of climate change in vulnerable populations, future longitudinal studies could enhance our understanding of these dynamics by tracking the evolution of CCA and depression over time, investigating and quantifying the mechanistic pathways in a regression model, and investigate specific coping mechanisms employed by female smallholder farmers to manage mental health episodes.

DECLARATIONS

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AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

All data used in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Committee on Human Research, Publications and Ethics (CHRPE) at the School of Medical Sciences, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana (Ref: CHRPE/AP/0103/25). Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no financial or personal relationships that may have inappropriately influenced them in writing this article.

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REFERENCES

- Abubakar, M., Saleem, A., Hajjaj, M., Faiz, H., Pragma, A., Jamil, R., Salim, S. S., Lateef, I. K., Singla, D., Ramar, R., Damara, I., & Shahid, L. (2024). Sex-specific differences in risk factors, comorbidities, diagnostic challenges, optimal management, and prognostic outcomes of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction: A comprehensive literature review. *Heart Failure Reviews*, 29(1), 235–256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10741-023-10369-4>
- Abunyewah, M., Erdiaw-Kwasie, M. O., Acheampong, A. O., Arhin, P., Okyere, S. A., Zanders, K., Frimpong, L. K., Byrne, M. K., & Lassa, J. (2023). Understanding climate change adaptation in Ghana: The role of climate change anxiety, experience, and knowledge. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 150, 103594. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2023.103594>
- Abunyewah, M., Okyere, S. A., Opoku Mensah, S., Erdiaw-Kwasie, M., Gajendran, T., & Byrne, M. K. (2024). Drought impact on peri-urban farmers' mental health in semi-arid Ghana: The moderating role of personal social capital. *Environmental Development*, 49, 100960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2023.100960>
- Acharibasam, J. W., & Anuga, S. W. (2018). Psychological distance of climate change and mental health risks assessment of smallholder farmers in Northern Ghana: Is habituation a threat to climate change? *Climate Risk Management*, 21, 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2018.04.002>
- Adam, I., Dayour, F., & Kimbu, A. N. (2023). Crisis-induced financial anxiety, social support, socio-psychological wellbeing, and commitment to work in the tourism sector. *Development Southern Africa*, 40(5), 1014–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0376835X.2023.2165042>
- Alare, R. S., Lawson, E. T., Mensah, A., Yeide, A., & Adiku, P. (2022). Assessing nuanced social networks and its implication for climate change adaptation in northwestern Ghana. *World Development Perspectives*, 25, 100390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wdp.2021.100390>
- Assan, E., Suvedi, M., Schmitt Olabisi, L., & Bansah, K. J. (2020). Climate change perceptions and challenges to adaptation among smallholder farmers in semi-arid Ghana: A gender analysis. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 182, 104247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2020.104247>
- Au, R. C. P., Watkins, D., Hattie, J., & Alexander, P. (2009). Reformulating the depression model of learned hopelessness for academic outcomes. *Educational Research Review*, 4(2), 103–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2009.04.001>
- Beck, A. T. (1996). *Manual for the beck depression inventory-II*. (No Title). <https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1370564063990947215>
- Berry, H. L., Hogan, A., Owen, J., Rickwood, D., & Fragar, L. (2011). Climate change and farmers' mental health: risks and responses. *Asia Pacific Journal of Public Health*, 23(2_suppl), 119S-132S. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1010539510392556>

- Chambers, R. (1994). The origins and practice of participatory rural appraisal. *World Development*, 22(7), 953–969. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X\(94\)90141-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X(94)90141-4)
- Chapola, J., Datta, R., & Waucaush-Warn, J. (2024). Climate change and its impact on the mental health well-being of Indigenous women in Western cities, Canada. *Journal of Community & Applied Social Psychology*, 34(3), e2807. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.2807>
- Chengane, S., Beseler, C. L., Duysen, E. G., & Rautiainen, R. H. (2021). Occupational stress among farm and ranch operators in the midwestern United States. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 2076. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12053-4>
- Cianconi, P., Betrò, S., & Janiri, L. (2020). The impact of climate change on mental health: a systematic descriptive review. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00074>
- Clayton, S. (2020). Climate anxiety: Psychological responses to climate change. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 74, 102263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2020.102263>
- Cochran, W. G. (1977). *Sampling techniques*. John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Cohen, J. (1992). A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*, 112(1), 155–159. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.112.1.155>
- Coker, A. O., Coker, O. O., & Sanni, D. (2018). Psychometric properties of the 21-item Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS-21). *African Research Review*, 12(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.4314/afrr.v12i2.13>
- Conrad, C. D. (2011). *The Handbook of Stress: Neuropsychological Effects on the Brain*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Daghagh Yazd, S., Wheeler, S. A., & Zuo, A. (2019). Key risk factors affecting farmers' mental health: a systematic review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(23), Article 23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16234849>
- Dibakoane, S., Siyongwana, P., & Shabalala, A. N. (2022). Vulnerability, impact and adaptation strategies of female farmers to climate variability. *Jàmbá : Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 14(1), 1302. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v14i1.1302>
- Domènech-Abella, J., Lara, E., Rubio-Valera, M., Olaya, B., Moneta, M. V., Rico-Urbe, L. A., Ayuso-Mateos, J. L., Mundó, J., & Haro, J. M. (2017). Loneliness and depression in the elderly: The role of social network. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 52(4), 381–390. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-017-1339-3>
- Dreyer, Z., Henn, Carolina, & Hill, C. (2019). Validation of the depression anxiety stress scale-21 (DASS-21) in a non-clinical sample of South African working adults. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 29(4), 346–353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14330237.2019.1647499>
- Du, X., & Pang, T. Y. (2015). Is dysregulation of the HPA-axis a core pathophysiology mediating comorbid depression in neurodegenerative diseases? *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2015.00032>
- Fanzo, J. (2017). From big to small: The significance of smallholder farms in the global food system. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 1(1), e15–e16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(17\)30011-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(17)30011-6)
- Fiske, A., Wetherell, J. L., & Gatz, M. (2009). Depression in older adults. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 5(Volume 5, 2009), 363–389. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.clinpsy.032408.153621>
- Green, S. B. (1991). How many subjects does it take to do a regression analysis. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, 26(3), 499–510. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327906mbr2603_7
- Gyasi, R. M. (2019). Social support, physical activity and psychological distress among community-dwelling older Ghanaians. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 81, 142–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archger.2018.11.016>
- Gyasi, R. M., & Phillips, D. R. (2020). Aging and the Rising Burden of Noncommunicable Diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa and other Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Call for Holistic Action. *The Gerontologist*, 60(5), 806–811. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnz102>
- Haines, V. A., Beggs, J. J., & Hurlbert, J. S. (2011). Neighborhood Disadvantage, Network Social Capital, and Depressive Symptoms. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 52(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022146510394951>
- Hajek, A., & König, H.-H. (2023). Climate Anxiety and Mental Health in Germany. *Climate*, 11(8), Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli11080158>
- Innocenti, M., Perilli, A., Santarelli, G., Carluccio, N., Zjalic, D., Acquadro Maran, D., Ciabini, L., & Cadeddu, C. (2023). How Does Climate Change Worry Influence the Relationship between Climate

- Change Anxiety and Eco-Paralysis? A Moderation Study. *Climate*, 11(9), Article 9.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/cli11090190>
- Jackson, J. C., Pandharipande, P. P., Girard, T. D., Brummel, N. E., Thompson, J. L., Hughes, C. G., Pun, B. T., Vasilevskis, E. E., Morandi, A., Shintani, A. K., Hopkins, R. O., Bernard, G. R., Dittus, R. S., & Ely, E. W. (2014). Depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, and functional disability in survivors of critical illness in the BRAIN-ICU study: A longitudinal cohort study. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 2(5), 369–379. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600\(14\)70051-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2213-2600(14)70051-7)
- Jiménez-Solomon, O., Primrose, R., Moon, I., Wall, M., Galfalvy, H., Méndez-Bustos, P., Cruz, A. G., Swarbrick, M., Laing, T., Vite, L., Kelley, M., Jennings, E., & Lewis-Fernández, R. (2022). Financial Hardship, Hope, and Life Satisfaction Among Un/Underemployed Individuals With Psychiatric Diagnoses: A Mediation Analysis. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2022.867421>
- Juster, R.-P., McEwen, B. S., & Lupien, S. J. (2010). Allostatic load biomarkers of chronic stress and impact on health and cognition. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 35(1), 2–16.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2009.10.002>
- Lagu, T., Hannon, N. S., Rothberg, M. B., Wells, A. S., Green, K. L., Windom, M. O., Dempsey, K. R., Pekow, P. S., Avrunin, J. S., Chen, A., & Lindenauer, P. K. (2013). Access to Subspecialty Care for Patients with Mobility Impairment. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 158(6), 441–446.
<https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-158-6-201303190-00003>
- Lambrecht, I. B. (2016). “As a husband I will love, lead, and provide.” Gendered access to land in Ghana. *World Development*, 88, 188–200.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2016.07.018>
- Léger-Goodes, T., Malboeuf-Hurtubise, C., Mastine, T., Gagnéux, M., Paradis, P.-O., & Camden, C. (2022). Eco-anxiety in children: A scoping review of the mental health impacts of the awareness of climate change. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.872544>
- Lutz, W., & Striessnig, E. (2015). Demographic aspects of climate change mitigation and adaptation. *Population Studies*, 69(sup1), S69–S76.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00324728.2014.969929>
- Manful, E., & Cudjoe, E. (2018). Is kinship failing? Views on informal support by families in contact with social services in Ghana. *Child & Family Social Work*, 23(4), 617–624.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/cfs.12452>
- McKenzie, K., & Harpham, T. (2006). *Social capital and mental health*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Miller, M. E., Nwosu, C. O., Nyamwanza, A. M., & Jacobs, P. T. (2023). Assessing psychosocial health impacts of climate adaptation: A critical review. *NEW SOLUTIONS: A Journal of Environmental and Occupational Health Policy*, 33(1), 37–50.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/10482911231173068>
- Nakagomi, A., Shiba, K., Kondo, K., & Kawachi, I. (2021). Can social capital moderate the impact of widowhood on depressive symptoms? A fixed-effects longitudinal analysis. *Aging & Mental Health*, 25(10), 1811–1820.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2020.1793296>
- Ojala, M., Cunsolo, A., Ogunbode, C. A., & Middleton, J. (2021). Anxiety, Worry, and Grief in a Time of Environmental and Climate Crisis: A Narrative Review. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 46(Volume 46, 2021), 35–58.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012220-022716>
- Organization, W. H. (2017). *Mental health of older adults [Fact sheet]*. World Health Organization Media Centre.
- Padhy, S. K., Sarkar, S., Panigrahi, M., & Paul, S. (2015). Mental health effects of climate change. *Indian Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 19(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5278.156997>
- Pihkala, P. (2022). The process of eco-Anxiety and ecological grief: A Narrative Review and a New Proposal. *Sustainability*, 14(24), Article 24.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416628>
- Polain, J. D., Berry, H. L., & Hoskin, J. O. (2011). Rapid change, climate adversity and the next ‘big dry’: Older farmers’ mental health. *Australian Journal of Rural Health*, 19(5), 239–243.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-1584.2011.01219.x>
- Prince, M. J., Harwood, R. H., Blizard, R. A., Thomas, A., & Mann, A. H. (1997). Social support deficits, loneliness and life events as risk factors for depression in old age. *The Gospel Oak Project VI. Psychological Medicine*, 27(2), 323–332.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291796004485>

- Reyes, M. E. S., Carmen, B. P. B., Luminarias, M. E. P., Mangulabnan, S. A. N. B., & Ogunbode, C. A. (2023). An investigation into the relationship between climate change anxiety and mental health among Gen Z Filipinos. *Current Psychology*, 42(9), 7448–7456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02099-3>
- Riden, H. E., Felt, E., & Pinkerton, K. E. (2021). The impact of climate change and extreme weather conditions on agricultural health and safety in California. *Climate Change and Global Public Health*, 353–368.
- Rothschild, J., & Haase, E. (2023). Women's mental health and climate change Part II: Socioeconomic stresses of climate change and eco-anxiety for women and their children. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*, 160(2), 414–420. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.14514>
- Sampaio, F., & Sequeira, C. (2022). Climate anxiety: Trigger or threat for mental disorders? *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6(2), e89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00008-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00008-0)
- Schneider, S. L. (2013). The international standard classification of education 2011. In G. Elisabeth Birkelund (Ed.), *Class and Stratification Analysis* (Vol. 30, pp. 365–379). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S0195-6310\(2013\)0000030017](https://doi.org/10.1108/S0195-6310(2013)0000030017)
- Schwartz, S. E. O., Benoit, L., Clayton, S., Parnes, M. F., Swenson, L., & Lowe, S. R. (2023). Climate change anxiety and mental health: Environmental activism as buffer. *Current Psychology*, 42(20), 16708–16721.
- Searle, K., & Gow, K. (2010). Do concerns about climate change lead to distress? *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 2(4), 362–379.
- Sivertsen, H., Bjørkløf, G. H., Engedal, K., Selbæk, G., & Helvik, A.-S. (2015). Depression and quality of life in older persons: A review. *Dementia and Geriatric Cognitive Disorders*, 40(5–6), 311–339.
- Tartour, A. I., Chivese, T., Eltayeb, S., Elamin, F. M., Fthenou, E., Seed Ahmed, M., & Babu, G. R. (2024). Prenatal psychological distress and 11 β -HSD2 gene expression in human placentas: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 166, 107060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2024.107060>
- Thoits, P. A. (2011). Mechanisms linking social ties and support to physical and mental health. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 52(2), 145–161. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022146510395592>
- Toader, M., & Roman, G. V. (2015). Family farming – examples for rural communities' development. *Agriculture and Agricultural Science Procedia*, 6, 89–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaspro.2015.08.043>
- Tsutsumimoto, K., Doi, T., Shimada, H., Makizako, H., Hotta, R., Nakakubo, S., & Suzuki, T. (2016). Combined effect of slow gait speed and depressive symptoms on incident disability in older adults. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 17(2), 123–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jamda.2015.08.012>
- Wang, P., Chen, X., Gong, J., & Jacques-Tiura, A. J. (2014). Reliability and validity of the personal social capital scale 16 and personal social capital scale 8: two short instruments for survey studies. *Social Indicators Research*, 119(2), 1133–1148. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-013-0540-3>
- Windle, M., & Windle, R. C. (2013). Recurrent depression, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes among middle-aged and older adult women. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 150(3), 895–902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2013.05.008>
- Yang, Y., Yang, M., Shi, Q., Wang, T., & Jiang, M. (2020). Risk factors for depression in patients with epilepsy: A meta-analysis. *Epilepsy & Behavior*, 106, 107030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yebeh.2020.107030>
- Yiridomoh, G. Y., Bonye, S. Z., Derbile, E. K., & Owusu, V. (2022). Women farmers' perceived indices of occurrence and severity of observed climate extremes in rural Savannah, Ghana. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 24(1), 810–831. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-021-01471-4>
- Zhang, Y., Kuang, J., Xin, Z., Fang, J., Song, R., Yang, Y., Song, P., Wang, Y., & Wang, J. (2023). Loneliness, social isolation, depression and anxiety among the elderly in Shanghai: Findings from a longitudinal study. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics*, 110, 104980.